

Launch of the DIGITISE Project to Drive Consumer Empowerment in the Digital Energy Market

Press Release, June 2024

The [DIGITISE project](#) (*Digital Innovative cross-sector services for Greater citizen Integration in a just energy Transition and Societal Empowerment*), funded by the European Commission under GA 101160671, aims to enhance digital literacy and empower consumers and consumers in the energy sector. It officially kicked off with a successful meeting held in Athens, Greece, on June 5–6, 2024. This ambitious initiative aspires to enable active engagement in digital energy activities and markets, promoting a pivotal role for consumers and prosumers in the ongoing energy transition.

DIGITISE is a forward-thinking project that amalgamates proven expertise and practical experience in energy systems, flexibility services, and energy markets. It emphasises social and human engagement within digital ecosystems, integrating technologies such as Innovative Cross-Sector Services, Digital Twins, DLT-enabled Marketplaces, AI Analytics, and Big Data Management. The project also prioritises interoperability and security, crafting a comprehensive consumer empowerment framework.

This framework will undergo extensive validation across one well-established Living Lab and four large-scale demonstration sites located in Greece, Spain, Croatia, and Ireland. These sites will involve various stakeholders, including consumers, prosumers, and business actors such as Retailers, Aggregators, and Local Energy Communities (LECs). Additionally, they will utilise diverse cross-domain data sources and heterogeneous energy and non-energy systems, accounting for multi-variate climatic and socio-economic characteristics.

The kick-off meeting in Athens marked the beginning of this innovative project, bringing together key stakeholders and laying the groundwork for the extensive work ahead. The event featured in-depth discussions on project goals, strategies, and implementation plans, setting the stage for a collaborative effort towards a more digitally empowered energy market.

DIGITSE outcomes will result from cooperation between 12 European entities, specialised in different aspects of the project: [UBITECH](#), [SUITE5](#), [MYTILINEOS](#), [CIRCE](#), [University College Dublin](#), [APPART](#), [UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA](#), [MIW](#), [ARDEN](#), [ZELENA ENERGETSKA ZADRUGA ZA USLUGE](#), [AUSTRALO](#), [MISSIONS PUBLIQUES](#).

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About DIGITISE:

Funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement number 101160671, DIGITISE is a project focused on enhancing the digital literacy and empowerment of consumers and prosumers in the energy sector. By integrating advanced technologies and fostering active engagement in digital energy activities and markets, DIGITISE aims to play a crucial role in the global energy transition.

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